

The extra-stabilization energy (l.f.s.e) and 14Dq values for 1 : 1 LN-EDTA chelates from the stability constant data were calculated¹⁶ assuming them to be octahedral. This procedure has been used to calculate the 14Dq values for the 1 : 1 LN-EDTA chelates in the present study. The highest value of 14Dq corresponds to 140 cm⁻¹, indicating a small crystal field splitting. In lanthanides the ligand field causes the splitting of seven-fold degenerate f-level into three sub-levels, a_{2u}, t_{2u} and t_{1u}. It has been shown¹⁷ that the electron pairing energy in the a_{2u} sub-level is about 8000 cm⁻¹ which is much higher than the present maximum value of 14Dq. This suggests a 'high-spin' distribution of electrons in the LN-EDTA chelates.

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Determination of Stability Constants of N-(2-Hydroxy-1-naphthalidene)-benzylamine Complexes with Cu²⁺, Ni²⁺, Co²⁺ and Cd²⁺

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It is observed from the literature available that no work on the solution stability constants of N-(2-hydroxy-1-naphthalidene)-benzylamine and its metal complexes has been reported so far. The present investigation is aimed at determining the stability constants of the complexes of Cu²⁺, Ni²⁺, Cd²⁺ and Co²⁺ with N-(2-hydroxy-1-naphthalidene)-benzylamine.

Experimental

2-Hydroxy-1-naphthaldehyde (Fluka) was dissolved in ethanol (5 g, ~200 ml) and was cooled to 0°. To this solution, freshly distilled benzylamine slightly in excess of the equimolar quantity was added dropwise with constant stirring. The solution was allowed to stand for 2 h at room temperature. The reaction was monitored by tlc to confirm the absence of traces of aldehyde. The compound separated out on dilution. It was then repeatedly crystallised from alcohol-water mixture (50 : 50) to get analytically pure yellow coloured compound. Observed m.p. 96° (Found : C, 82.80 ; H, 5.79 ; N, 5.38. Calcd. for C₁₈H₁₅ON ; C 82.73, H, 5.74 ; N, 5.32%).

The Calvin-Bjerrum's pH titration technique as adapted by Irving and Rossotti¹ was used to determine the dissociation constant of the reagent and formation constants of its metal complexes at 30 ± 0.1° in 75 : 25 v/v dioxane-water. The Elico Model LI 15 pH meter was employed for pH determinations. During the titration oxygen free nitrogen presaturated with solvent mixture was bubbled through solution. The solutions of metal perchlorates were prepared using metal carbonates or oxides (A.R. grade). All these were standardised complexometrically by EDTA titrations².

The solutions titrated potentiometrically against standard carbonate free sodium hydroxide (1.08 M) solution were i) 5 ml (0.16 M) HClO₄ + 5 ml (0.64 M) NaClO₄ + 30 ml dioxane; (ii) 5 ml (0.16 M) HClO₄ + 5 ml (0.64 M) NaClO₄ + requisite amount of reagent accurately weighed to give 0.004 M reagent concentration in the final solution + 30 ml dioxane; and (iii) 5 ml (0.64 M) NaClO₄ + 5 ml metal perchlorate (0.008 M) in 0.16 M HClO₄ + the requisite amount of reagent accurately weighed to give 0.004 M reagent concentration in final solution + 30 ml dioxane. The titrations were performed in duplicate to test for reproducibility.

NOTES

Results and Discussion

It may be mentioned that the reagent does not undergo hydrolysis under the experimental conditions. This was indicated by rapid attainment of equilibrium during titration and by absence of any significant drift in pH even after two hours.

The phenolic group of the ligand takes part in the complex formation and the proton is replaced from it by the metal ion. As only one proton per ligand molecule is liberated during complexation, \bar{Y} , the number of dissociable protons attached to each ligand molecule is one.

The plot of \bar{n}_A versus B extends over a range of $0.24 < \bar{n}_A < 2.08$, indicating the formation of species HL and H_2L . From this formation curve (Fig. 1), pK_1^H which corresponds to the association of proton to phenoxide ion of the reagent and pK_2^H which corresponds to the association of proton to nitrogen of the reagent were obtained at $\bar{n}_A = 0.5$ and 1.5, respectively. However, the difference between pK_1^H and pK_2^H was less than 1.78 log units and the non-wave nature of formation curve indicates that the formation of the species HL and H_2L does not take place in well defined separate steps. Hence they were better calculated by least square method and recorded.

Fig. 1. N-[2-Hydroxy-1-naphthalidene]-benzylamine formation curve.

The \bar{n} and pL values were calculated from the titration curves using solutions (ii) and (iii). The \bar{n} values were plotted against the corresponding pL values to get the formation curves of the metal complex equilibria (Fig. 2). The values of \bar{n} , $0.097 < \bar{n} <$

0.902 , indicate the complete formation of 1 : 1 complexes for Cu^{2+} and Co^{2+} . The $\log K_1$ values of these complexes were determined by half integral method. The plot of $\log [\bar{n}/(1-\bar{n})]$ vs pL was also drawn for these systems. The values of $\log K_1$ evaluated from these plots agree quite well with those obtained by half integral method.

Fig. 2. Metal-ligand system of N-[2-hydroxy-1-naphthalidene]-benzylamine formation curves.

The \bar{n} values extend over a range of $0.083 < \bar{n} < 0.40$ for Cd^{2+} and Ni^{2+} systems. Hence $\log K_1$ values of these metal systems were determined by extrapolation of the plot of $\log [\bar{n}/(1-\bar{n})]$ vs pL .

The most representative values are recorded in Table 1. The order of stability constants of the chelates is found to be $Cu^{2+} > Co^{2+} > Ni^{2+} > Cd^{2+}$.

TABLE 1—STEPWISE STABILITY CONSTANTS OF VARIOUS COMPLEXES

	$t = 30^\circ$				
	$\mu = 0.1 M$				
	H	Cu^{2+}	Co^{2+}	Cd^{2+}	Ni^{2+}
$\log K_1$	9.00	10.03	6.02	4.55	5.35
$\log K_2^*$	7.93	—	—	—	—

*Could not be evaluated because of precipitation of metal ions probably due to metal ions hydrolysis.

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